

ISSN: 3060-4613

13.00.00	13.00.06	01.00.00
13.00.01	13.00.07	02.00.00
13.00.02	13.00.08	03.00.00
13.00.03	13.00.09	09.00.00
13.00.04	07.00.00	10.00.00
13.00.05	19.00.00	11.00.00

№6/2025

M AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogik, psixometodologik va tabiiy fanlarga
ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 400 sahifa,
5-iyun, 2025-yil.

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Asos: OAK Pedagogik texnologiyalar va psixologik tadqiqotlar bo’yicha ekspert kengashi tavsiyasi (29-10-2024-y.; №10); OAK Tartib-qoida komissiyasi qarori (30-10-2024-y., №10/24); OAK Rayosatining qarori (31-10-2024-y., №363/5).

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo’yicha
ro’yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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METHODOLOGY FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF TRAINING 10–12-YEAR-OLD TENNIS PLAYERS

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Abstract: The study employed a non-traditional set of exercises to enhance the technical training of tennis players aged 10–12 years. After a 6-month training cycle, the accuracy of strokes was assessed by calculating the ratio of the number of clear and unclear balls aimed at the target located on the right side at a 60° angle from a distance of 7 meters. The training effectiveness was evaluated accordingly.

Key words: tennis players, technique, technical training, forehand strokes, backhand strokes.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotda 10–12 yoshli tennischilarning texnik tayyorgarligini oshirish maqsadida an'anaviy bo'lmagan mashqlar majmuasi qo'llanildi. 6 oylik mashg'ulotlardan so'ng zarba aniqligi baholandi – bu, 60° burchak ostida o'ng tomondagi nishonga 7 metr masofadan yo'naltirilgan to'g'ri va noto'g'ri zarbalar soni nisbatiga asoslanib hisoblandi. Shundan kelib chiqib, texnik tayyorgarlik samaradorligi aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: tennischilar, texnika, texnik tayyorgarlik, forhend zarbasi, bekhend zarbasi.

Аннотация: В исследовании применён нетрадиционный комплекс упражнений для совершенствования технической подготовки теннисистов в возрасте 10–12 лет. Через 6 месяцев точность ударов оценивалась на основе соотношения количества точных и неточных мячей, направленных в цель с правой стороны под углом 60° с расстояния 7 метров. Эффективность подготовки определялась по этим данным.

Ключевые слова: теннисисты, техника, техническая подготовка, удары справа, удары слева.

INTRODUCTION

As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated, no matter what goals we set for ourselves and what great deeds we strive to accomplish, all our noble actions and good intentions are based on raising our children to be spiritually healthy. Their happiness is embodied in the dream of seeing a prosperous future and nurturing a generation that is ready for tomorrow – a generation with no equal in the world.

The remarkable success of today's healthy and well-rounded generation of our country on the global stage is the result of the special attention paid to the development of children's sports ^[1,7].

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

It should be noted that the optimization of the modern training system and the implementation of innovative strategies in the training process are among the key tasks in preparing young reserve athletes, many of whom currently represent the national teams of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Sports schools serve as one of the main pillars in the effective execution of these essential responsibilities.

In fact, sports and mass physical education have become a reliable form of psychological support for the younger generation raised in a healthy lifestyle. Therefore, sports schools carry the vital responsibility of educating active citizens and patriots of their country. Based on these considerations, enhancing the effectiveness of non-traditional exercises in the initial stages of tennis training is recognized as one of the most pressing objectives.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

To develop an effective methodology for improving the technical training of tennis players aged 10–12 years.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted among two groups of children aged 10–12 years who had recently begun playing tennis – the control group ($n = 12$) and the experimental group ($n = 12$).

The content and conditions of the pedagogical experiment were as follows:

Children in the control group participated in regular tennis training according to the standard curriculum provided by sports schools.

During the study period, the experimental group performed the following additional exercises:

1. Two tennis players passed the ball to each other while initially standing 6 meters apart, with a gymnastic ring suspended at a height of 1 meter between them. Every 3 months, the distance was increased to 8, 10, and 12 meters.

The exercise was performed twice for 10 minutes each – on both the right and left sides. The total number of passes was recorded, and the accuracy of passes from each side (clear and fuzzy passes) was evaluated separately.

2. Two parallel plywood targets, each 1–2 meters long, were placed on the net at a distance of 1 meter from the tennis posts.

In this exercise, two tennis players stood on the right side of their court and hit a ball thrown by a partner from the opposite side, aiming at their designated target.

The evaluation of this task was conducted using the same criteria as in the first exercise.

3. Players alternately aimed at two targets (each 50 cm² in area), drawn on a wall at a height of 1.3 meters and 1.5 meters apart.

The evaluation procedure was consistent with that of the first exercise.

Additionally, the following non-traditional exercises were performed at three intervals: before each load test, 10 minutes into the session, and 20 minutes after completing the activity:

- (a) Running clockwise (3 minutes) and counterclockwise (3 minutes) in a circle with a 3-meter diameter.

- (b) Jumping straight up and performing a 360° spin mid-air before landing on the ground.

Right and left rotations were each performed 10 times.

- (c) Bending the torso forward to a 90° angle while holding a stick with the right hand pressed to the ground, performing 10 clockwise turns; then switching the stick to the left hand and performing 10 counterclockwise turns. Rotation speed was moderate.

- (d) While standing with eyes closed, turning the head 30° to the right and 30° to the left with maximum amplitude.

- (e) Two tennis players facing each other extended their arms and performed 10 turns to the right and 10 to the left.

Prior to the pedagogical experiment, as well as after 3 months and 6 months, in both the control and experimental groups:

The accuracy of stroke execution (number of successful hits) was measured based on the ratio of the sum of clear and fuzzy balls aimed at targets located on the right side during the third test exercise, at a distance of 7 meters and an angle of 60°.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results obtained indicate that, prior to the pedagogical study, individual and average statistical indicators of both the control and experimental groups did not differ significantly from one another. In particular, the test result for head rotation to the right with maximum amplitude – measured while standing with eyes closed and before losing balance – was 16.7 ± 1.01 seconds in the control group and 15.9 ± 1.07 seconds in the experimental group. These findings suggest that the functional capacity of the vestibular analyzer was weak in both groups when subjected to rotational acceleration.

This situation demonstrates a lack of functional connectivity between the vestibular analyzer and the motion and visual analyzers. It is well known that such functional connections are developed through targeted training, and their formation plays a crucial role in athletic performance – particularly in executing rapid and precise movements in dynamic conditions.

At the beginning of the pedagogical study, and again after the 3rd and 6th months, the results revealed that the functional stability of the vestibular analyzer in the control group increased gradually but inconsistently. In contrast, the experimental group exhibited smoother, more stable progression in this quality parameter – reflecting a clear “ladder-like” growth dynamic. These growth patterns are illustrated in the accompanying diagrams.

Figure 1: Development of functional stability of the vestibular analyzer in the control and experimental groups during a pedagogical study

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

As illustrated in the diagram, the results obtained prior to the pedagogical study did not differ significantly between the two groups. For example, in the control group, the functional stability of the vestibular analyzer under rotational acceleration was 16.7 seconds, whereas in the experimental group, the value of this indicator was slightly lower – 15.9 seconds. However, after 3 months, the exercise program implemented in the experimental group began to demonstrate its effectiveness. Specifically, the indicator in the control group increased to 19.3 seconds, while in the experimental group, vestibular stasis reached 27.5 seconds.

After 6 months of the pedagogical study, vestibular stasis in the experimental group increased from 27.5 seconds to 41.9 seconds. The fact that this final result exceeded the initial indicator by 23.7 seconds strongly confirms the effectiveness of the exercise complex applied in the experimental group. In contrast, in the control group, vestibular stasis increased by only 2.6 seconds after 3 months, and then decreased by 1.1 seconds after 6 months, indicating a lack of sustained improvement.

Summary of Findings

Based on the above results, it can be concluded that the series of specialized and non-specialized (circular acceleration-based) exercises conducted in the experimental group not only enhanced the functional stability of the vestibular analyzer but also strengthened its interaction with the visual and motor analyzers. This functional synergy significantly contributed to improving the accuracy of motor responses – particularly stroke precision in tennis.

Therefore, the set of special and non-traditional exercises developed and tested within the framework of this pedagogical research can be recommended as an effective technological approach for training tennis players – especially in the formation and enhancement of stroke accuracy.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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2025. №6

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.